

Comparison of speed loop control methods for IPM motor in electric vehicles

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ABSTRACT

With its outstanding features, such as high efficiency and torque-producing capability compared with the induction motor, the interior permanent magnet synchronous motor (IPMSM) has been increasingly researched and used for electric vehicles. The speed control strategy for both low and high speeds of the IPMSM is studied in conjunction with controllers based on the field-oriented control (FOC) structure to ensure accurate and stable system response under various operating conditions. This paper focuses on three control methods: sliding mode control (SMC), backstepping (BSP), and proportional integral (PI) for the speed loop to enhance system stability. Coupled with the presence of load disturbances, environmental disturbances, and uncertainties in parameters, comparisons and observations regarding the three methods can be made to conclude system stability and performance. Finally, simulation results on MATLAB/Simulink software confirm the effectiveness and validity of the proposed speed controllers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Depleting fossil fuels and environmental pollution have become significant issues that any nation worldwide faces, which is partially attributable to means of transportation. Therefore, electric vehicles are currently considered a suitable solution to address these two issues. The interior permanent magnet synchronous motor (IPMSM) possesses advantages such as high efficiency, capability of generating ample torque, wide speed adjustment range, and high power density, making it an attractive choice in various fields such as electric vehicle manufacturing, wind power, aerospace, and widely applied in other industrial sectors [1]. When the motor operates at high speed, it is limited by voltage and energy, which may cause a decrease in output torque, current, and speed; the IPMSM can widen the speed adjustment range by controlling the torque in the weakening flux region [2]. To maximize the potential of this kind of motor, the maximum torque per ampere (MTPA) method is preferred [3], [4]. Widely used methods in IPMSM drives include direct torque control (DTC) and field-oriented control (FOC) [5]-[8], which are accompanied by various control methods and controllers applied to the speed loops. Conventional proportional integral (PI) controllers can control the motor [9], [10], but disturbances and changes in the motor's parameters have caused system instability. Nowadays, control theory is continuously evolving, and various control techniques have been widely utilized, such as sliding mode control (SMC), backstepping control, sliding mode variable structure

control (SMVSC), intelligent control, fuzzy control, neural networks, and adaptive control, which can operate IPMSM with high efficiency [11]-[20].

Dianov *et al.* [21] utilized the MTPA algorithm for the IPMSM drive system with PI controllers. Kirad *et al.* [22] applied sensorless backstepping technique with Kalman filtering to enhance motor performance. Feng *et al.* [23] developed a novel sliding mode control technology and comprehensive evaluation method for speed control of IPMSM to provide a rational assessment of speed control for synchronous PMSMs in various operating stages. Zhang *et al.* [24] designed and controlled field weakening of IPMSM for electric vehicles to demonstrate good dynamic performance and stable operation with the ability to extend speed up to four times the rated value. Belkacem *et al.* [25] compared backstepping sliding mode and reverse control for some vehicle components to demonstrate effectiveness and durability against external disturbances and different road conditions. Hosseini and Tabatabaei [26] controlled current and speed of IPMSM using segmented adaptive sliding mode control based on MTPA for current loop. Tung *et al.* [27] applied sliding mode observer for sensorless speed-controlled IPMSM with permanent magnet excitation along the axial magnetic field. Foo and Rahman [28] controlled MTPA in sensorless sliding mode for IPMSM drive system using sliding mode observer and high frequency (HF) signal transmission. Hashemi *et al.* [29] developed high-performance PI-based controllers for IPM motor drive system.

However, the existing studies have yet to propose and implement various control methods to replace PI and proportional integral derivative (PID) controllers for IPMSM motors operating in the field weakening region applicable to electric vehicles. Therefore, this paper will propose three different approaches to design controllers for the speed loop circuit applicable to electric cars, specifically VinFast electric vehicles. Finally, simulation results on MATLAB/Simulink software verified the correctness of the Authors' research.

2. MODELLING DRIVE SYSTEM OF ELECTRIC VEHICLES

2.1. Mathematical model of the IPMSM motor

The IPMSM model is represented in the d-q coordinate system as (1) [30]-[33]. Where $U_{sd}, U_{sq}, i_{sd}, i_{sq}$ R_s, L_{sd}, L_{sq} are voltages, currents, resistance, inductances of the stator on dq-axis, ω_s is the angular velocity of the motor, ψ_p is the rotor flux, p_p is the number of pole pairs of the motor, T_e is the motor output torque, ψ_{sd}, ψ_{sq} are the stator flux on the dq-axis, T_L is the load torque, J is the moment of inertia of the motor, $T_{sd} = \frac{L_{sd}}{R_s}$ is the d-axis time constant of the stator circuit and $T_{sq} = \frac{L_{sq}}{R_s}$ is the q-axis time constant of the stator circuit.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{di_{sd}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{T_{sd}} i_{sd} + \omega_s \frac{L_{sq}}{L_{sd}} i_{sq} + \frac{1}{L_{sd}} U_{sd} \\ \frac{di_{sq}}{dt} = -\omega_s \frac{L_{sq}}{L_{sd}} i_{sd} - \frac{1}{T_{sq}} i_{sq} + \frac{1}{L_{sq}} U_{sq} - \omega_s \frac{\psi_p}{L_{sq}} \\ \psi_{sd} = L_{sd} i_{sd} + \psi_p \\ \psi_{sq} = L_{sq} i_{sq} \\ T_e = \frac{3}{2} p_p (\psi_p i_{sq} - i_{sd} i_{sq} (L_{sd} - L_{sq})) \\ T_e - T_L = \frac{J}{p_p} \frac{d\omega}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Modeling the forces acting on the electric vehicle

As the vehicle moves, the atmosphere will impede its motion. This resistance force consists the air resistance and the vehicle's friction with the air [34]. These two components combined form the wind resistance force, which is calculated by (2).

$$F_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A_f (v_{veh} + v_{wind})^2 \quad (2)$$

Where ρ is the air density, C_d is the coefficient of air resistance (typically: $0.2 < C_d < 0.4$); A_f is the frontal area of the vehicle's body (cross-sectional area), and v_{wind} is the wind speed.

For rolling resistance, we only consider the rolling friction on a rigid road surface, and in the ideal case where all wheels have the same conditions, the rolling friction force can be calculated as (3) [5].

$$F_{roll} = f_r m_v g \cos \alpha \quad (3)$$

Where m_v is the total mass of the vehicle and passengers, g is the gravitational acceleration, α is the slope angle, f_r is the coefficient of rolling resistance calculated by (4). With v_{veh} being the velocity of the vehicle.

$$f_r = 0.01 \left(1 + \frac{3.6}{100} v_{veh} \right) \quad (4)$$

3. SPEED LOOP CONTROL DESIGN

Figure 1 presents the control structure based on the principle of field-oriented control on the dq -axis system to control the speed above the rated speed in the field weakening region. At the same time, the torque reaches the maximum value. The speed loop controllers are PI, backstepping, and sliding mode control to compare and evaluate the quality of speed control.

Figure 1. The field-oriented control structure of IPM

3.1. The sliding mode control design

Figure 2 shows the SMC controller structure, which defines the error between the desired and feedback angular velocity as (5), that $e = \omega - \omega^*$. Taking the derivative of the error as in (5).

$$\dot{e} = \dot{\omega} - \dot{\omega}^* = \frac{p_p}{J} (T_e - T_L) - \dot{\omega}^* \quad (5)$$

J is the moment of inertia, T_L is the load torque, p_p is the number of pole pairs. Choosing the Lyapunov function $V = \frac{1}{2} s^2$ [14]. The derivative of V is written as (6).

$$\dot{V} = s \cdot \dot{s} \quad (6)$$

To ensure stability conditions $\dot{V} < 0$, the sliding surface s is defined as follows: $s = e \Rightarrow \dot{s} = \dot{e}$. Setting $\dot{s} = 0$ we obtain the robust control component, as in (7).

$$T_e = \frac{-J}{p_p} \left(-\frac{p_p}{J} T_L - \dot{\omega}^* \right) \quad (7)$$

The system is stable when V is positive definite, continuously differentiable with first-order derivatives, and negative definite [35]. To ensure $s \cdot \dot{s} < 0$, the exponential reaching law is chosen to have the following form [36].

$$\dot{s} = -\varepsilon \operatorname{sgn}(s) - ks, \varepsilon > 0, k > 0 \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the control signal is designed as (9).

$$T_e = \frac{-J}{p_p} \left(ks - \frac{p_p}{J} T_L - \dot{\omega}^* + \varepsilon \operatorname{sgn}(s) \right) \quad (9)$$

With $k = 100$, $\varepsilon = 10$. Proving stability as (10).

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= s \cdot \dot{s} = \dot{e} = \dot{\omega} - \dot{\omega}^* = s \left[\frac{p_p}{J} (T_e - T_L) - \dot{\omega}^* \right] \\ &= s \left[\frac{p_p}{J} \left(\frac{-J}{p_p} \left(ks - \frac{p_p}{J} T_L - \dot{\omega}^* + \varepsilon \operatorname{sgn}(s) \right) - T_L \right) - \dot{\omega}^* \right] \\ &= s(-ks - \varepsilon \operatorname{sgn}(s)) = -(\varepsilon|s| + ks^2) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

3.2. The backstepping control design

Figure 3 shows the BSP controller structure. Let's define the error signal as: $e = \omega - \omega^*$, taking the derivative of both sides as in (11).

$$\dot{e} = \dot{\omega} - \dot{\omega}^* = \frac{p_p}{J}(T_e - T_L) - \dot{\omega}^* \tag{11}$$

Choosing the Lyapunov function $V = \frac{1}{2}e^2$. Taking the derivative of V [1]: $\dot{V} = e \cdot \dot{e}$. Choosing the control parameter $k > 0$ such as (12).

$$\dot{e} = -ke \Rightarrow \dot{V} = e \cdot (-ke) = -ke^2 < 0 \tag{12}$$

Substituting $\dot{e} = -ke$ into (11), we obtain (13). With $k = 100$.

$$\frac{p_p}{J}(T_e - T_L) - \dot{\omega}^* = -ke \Rightarrow T_e = T_L - \frac{J}{p_p}(ke - \dot{\omega}^*) \tag{13}$$

3.3. The PI controller design

When synthesizing the speed loop circuit, as shown in Figure 4, we consider the entire current loop as a function of the optimal module standard and regard the component $(L_{sd} - L_{sq})i_{sd}i_{sq}$ as noise [37]-[39]. The speed control loop with the transfer function, as (14).

$$P = \frac{1}{K_i(1+2T_{si}p+2T_{si}^2p^2)} \cdot \frac{3p_p\psi_p}{2} \cdot \frac{K_\omega}{T_\omega p+1} \tag{14}$$

With $T_{si} = 2T_i$. According to the optimal module standard, select the normalized function, as (15).

$$F_c = \frac{1}{2T^2\sigma s^2+2T\sigma s+1} \tag{15}$$

Set $K = 2K_i/(3p_c \cdot \psi_p)$. The controller is as (16).

$$R_\omega = \frac{F_c}{(1-F_c)P} = \frac{(1+2T_{si}p+2T_{si}^2p^2) \cdot K \cdot (1+T_\omega p) \cdot Jp}{2p_c K_\omega (1+T_\sigma p) T_\sigma p} \tag{16}$$

Figure 2. SMC controller structure

Figure 3. BSP controller structure

Eliminate high-order components, as (17).

$$R_\omega = \frac{(1+2T_{si}p).K.(1+T_\omega p).Jp}{2p_p K_\omega (1+T_\sigma p) T_\sigma p} = \frac{[1+(2T_{si}+T_\omega)].K.Jp}{2p_p K_\omega (1+T_\sigma p) T_\sigma p} \quad (17)$$

Deselect: $T_\sigma = T_{s\omega} = 2T_{si} + T_\omega$; We have $R_\omega = \frac{K.Jp}{2p_c K_\omega T_{s\omega} p}$.

The controller becomes a simple stage incapable of eliminating static error while there is load disturbance. The symmetric optimal synthesis method can overcome this drawback. Choosing the standard function according to symmetric optimization as (18).

$$F_c = \frac{1+4T_\sigma p}{1+4T_\sigma p+8T^2_\sigma p^2+8T^3_\sigma p^3} \quad (18)$$

Where $R_\omega = \frac{F_c}{(1-F_c)p}$ and setting $T_\sigma = T_{s\omega} = 2T_{si} + T_\omega$

From there, we obtain (19).

$$R_\omega = \frac{F_c}{(1-F_c)p} = \frac{(1+2T_{si}p+2T^2_{si}p^2).K.(1+T_\omega p)(1+4T_\sigma p).Jp}{8p_p K_\omega (1+T_\sigma p) T^2_\sigma p^2} \quad (19)$$

Eliminating the high-order terms with (20).

$$R_\omega = \frac{(1+2T_{si}p).K.(1+T_\omega p)(1+4T_\sigma p).Jp}{8p_p K_\omega (1+T_\sigma p) T^2_\sigma p^2} = \frac{[1+(2T_{si}+T_\omega)p].K.(1+4T_\sigma p).J}{8p_p K_\omega (1+T_\sigma p) T^2_\sigma p} = \frac{K.(1+4T_\sigma p).J}{8p_p K_\omega T^2_\sigma p} \quad (20)$$

Obtaining the speed controller as (21).

$$R_\omega = \frac{K.J}{2p_p K_\omega T_{s\omega}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{4.T_{s\omega}.p}\right) \quad (21)$$

Figure 4. Speed loop circuit

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The theoretical studies validated through responses simulated on MATLAB software include three control methods for the speed loop of the FOC structure applied in electric vehicles. The responses are implemented in MATLAB/ Simulink using the simulation parameters from Tables 1 and 2. The speed profile is based on Europe ECE's standard urban cycle [40]. The speed response of the electric vehicle transmission control system using PI, BSP, and SMC is illustrated in Figure 5. Figure 5 compares the speed response results of three methods: PI, BSP, and SMC. SMC and BSP demonstrate relatively short transient response times of about 0.07 s, whereas PI responds slower, around 0.2 s. Moreover, during the transition from acceleration to steady-state, an overshoot occurred. From Figure 5, we can observe that the overshoot of PI is the largest, leading to oscillation and a more extended response time, followed by BSP and, finally, SMC.

The three control methods, PI, BSP, and SMC, have been conducted when the load changes, and the results are presented in Figure 6. Overall, when operating at speeds higher than the rated speed (1200 rpm), all three methods show a decrease in electromagnetic torque to increase the speed. This leads to a higher peak value of the torque oscillation in the PI method and a larger amplitude of oscillation, potentially affecting the system's stability. Conversely, we observe a smaller peak value of the electromagnetic torque oscillation in SMC, with a lower amplitude of oscillation and smaller torque. This result indicates that the system is less affected by load disturbances.

Figure 7 illustrates the waveforms of i_{sd} and i_{sq} . Looking at Figure 7(a), we can observe that the two currents i_{sd} and i_{sq} have been decoupled, with i_{sd} being controlled to be less than 0. Examining Figure 7(b) and Figure 7(c), during sudden load changes in PI and BSP control, i_{sd} and i_{sq} currents oscillate and exhibit more giant spikes, affecting the system's stability. In contrast, SMC exhibits more minor oscillations, providing better response and being less affected by load changes.

Table 1. Parameters of motor IPM

Parameters	Symbol	Value	Unit
Stator resistance	R_s	0.0065	Ohm
d-axis inductance	L_{sd}	0.001597	H
q-axis inductance	L_{sq}	0.002057	H
Inertia torque	J	0.09	kg.m ²
Number of pole pairs	p_p	3	
DC voltage	V_{dc}	550	V

Table 2. Parameters of an electric car

Parameters	Value	Unit
Vehicle weight + load	2018	kg
Wheel radius	0.3	m
Transmission ratio	9.73	
Maximum speed	130	km/h
Effective area	2.3	m ²
Air density	1.25	kg/m ³
Road gradient	0	
Rolling resistance coefficient	0.02	

Figure 5. The speed response

Figure 6. Torque response as load changes

Figure 7. Current response to sudden load changes: (a) comparison of the current responses i_{sd} and i_{sq} of three methods, (b) zoom out i_{sd} , and (c) zoom out i_{sq}

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a comparison of three control methods, PI, SMC, and BSP, for the speed control loop of the IPM motor to evaluate them based on criteria such as stability, response time, and accuracy in speed control even when the load changes. Simulation results have shown that the sliding mode control (SMC) method yielded the best results among the three compared methods. SMC ensures high stability and fast response time and minimizes control errors, especially under dynamic and noisy conditions while the overshoot of PI is the largest, leading to oscillation and more extended response time; PI and BSP cause i_{sd} and i_{sq} currents to oscillate as load changes. These results suggest that SMC can be effectively applied in IPM control systems, particularly when high precision and fast response are required. This research provides a foundation for selecting the appropriate control method in IPM motor control applications.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
An Thi Hoai Thu Anh	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Tran Van Nhu		✓				✓	✓		✓		✓			
Tran Trong Hieu			✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓

C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nterpretation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : **O**rganizing - **O**riginal Draft

E : **E**diting - **E**diting

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in IJPEDS at DOI: 10.11591/ijped.v15.i4.ppab-cd.

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